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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF STRUCTURED INDIVIDUALIZED
PHARMACIST INTERVENTION PROGRAMME ON
ECONOMIC, CLINICAL AND HUMANISTIC OUTCOMES OF
COPD PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY ROHINI SUPER
SPECIALITY HOSPITAL****Nallagatla Sai Kiran*, Dr.V. Umarani, DR.K. Nagasree, Dr.K. Shrivankumar**¹Department Of Pharmacy Practice, Samskruti College Of Pharmacy, Ghatkesar, Telangana.
501301.**Abstract:**

Neonatal jaundice is a yellowish discoloration of the white part of the eyes and skin in a newborn baby due to high bilirubin levels. Other symptoms may include excess sleepiness or poor feeding. Complications may include seizures, cerebral palsy, or kernicterus. The need for treatment depends on bilirubin levels, the age of the child, and the underlying cause. Treatments may include more frequent feeding, phototherapy, or exchange transfusions. In those who are born early more aggressive treatment tends to be required. Physiologic jaundice generally lasts less than seven days. It aims to assess and manage the incidence of jaundice in neonates The study conducted, in neonates who are either born in primary care or discharged to primary care within the first few hours to days of life. A maternity care assistant (MCA) provides postpartum care to mother and neonate during daytime for the first 8 days after delivery. The MCA is supervised by a community midwife, who visits the family at least three times in the first week. Medical doctors are only involved in the care of otherwise healthy neonates if consulted by the community midwife. Jaundice is common in otherwise healthy neonates cared for in primary care. TSB quantification was not always performed in very jaundiced neonates, and not all neonates received phototherapy when indicated. Quality improvement initiatives are required, including alternative approaches to identifying potentially severe jaundice.

KEYWORDS: Maternity care assistant, Bilirubin levels, Community midwife, Neonates

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INTRODUCTION:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is characterized by a progressive airflow limitation in the lungs, which, unlike asthma, is not fully reversible by medication.¹ However, adherence to therapy improves management of symptoms and delays disease progression. Patients' awareness and knowledge about the disease are important in leading a normal life. COPD leads to suffering, disability, hospitalization, loss of productivity and high cost to the patient and society.¹

COPD has been described as "10% medication and 90% education."¹ Inclusion of pharmacists in the healthcare team plays a pivotal role in smoking cessation and educational interventions, thereby decreasing disease progression, improving medication adherence and inhaler use. Only 17% of patients with chronic disease achieve perfect medication adherence.² Level of adherence decreases when patients are required to master a specific technique (inhaler use). Individuals with COPD face both medication adherence and inhaler use as major barriers, which emphasize the potential role of clinical pharmacists as COPD patient educators.²

Poor compliance and non-adherence are social issues, where patient's beliefs and myths play a role in shaping attitudes and practices.³ Pharmacist should engage with all patients and provide required health education that would assist them in self-care. Further, motivation plays a crucial role in promoting self-care.⁴ Patients who voluntarily involve themselves in self-care are open to educational interventions, which may be updated easily, particularly in matters of medicines, disease and lifestyle modifications. In order to improve overall well-being of the patient, treatment should not be restricted to medication management strategy alone. Multi factorial approaches that include comprehensive health education should be considered.

Many individuals with COPD experience significant relief after sharing their feelings with educators. Patient involvement is essential for the effective care of COPD patients. Providing patient-education, self-assurance, motivation and support constitute a fundamental duty of health professionals. Therefore, educational modules to improve self-care are vital components of any effective management strategy.

COPD significantly impairs health related quality of life (HRQoL).^{5,6} Acute exacerbation of COPD (AECOPD) is associated with reduced mobility and limits daily activities, thereby negatively affecting HRQoL.⁷ Addressing various aspects of COPD is perhaps best achieved by employing a multidisciplinary team to work through all stages of patient management.⁸ COPD is also a burden to care givers, as their support becomes crucial in handling

symptoms, coping with physical disabilities and managing emotional distress. Some studies show that patients with COPD become frustrated and anxious about symptom management, find it difficult to cope with inappropriate food habits, which together lead to a limited social life.^{8, 9}

Lack of adherence to medical therapies is a growing concern. Clancy (Director of the Agency for Health Research and Quality, WHO) defined lack of adherence as "a new pharmacological problem". As per WHO, "maximizing the effectiveness of investments aimed at increasing compliance may have a far better impact on people's health than any other progress in the therapeutic arena."¹⁰ Adherence to the therapy improves management of the symptoms and delay in disease progression.

Adherence is defined as "the extent to which a person's behavior (in terms of taking medications, following diets, or executing lifestyle changes) coincides with medical or health advice."¹¹ Patient non-adherence is one of the best recorded but least understood health-related actions.¹² COPD patients are non-adherent with their treatment recommendations both intentionally and unintentionally.¹³ However, better medication adherence was associated with decrease in the number of emergency department visits and length of hospital stay among patients with chronic respiratory diseases.¹⁴

"Drugs don't work in patients who don't take them". This quote by C. Everett Koop is not as obvious as it might seem. In order for a drug to be useful, not only should the active ingredient be effective, its delivery must be optimal, and more importantly, the patient must adhere to the therapy.¹⁰ Intentional non-adherence is a decision taken by patients who fail to fill prescribed therapy. Approximately 15% of patients do not fill a new prescription and usually discontinue therapy after about six months. Unintentional non-adherence could be considered as a passive process; the patients fail to adhere to prescribing instructions for many reasons outside their control (old age, social conditions etc).¹⁰

Several investigators have suggested that health professionals' style of communication with the patient may alter the patient's ability and tendency for medication adherence.¹⁵ Although health professionals may be increasingly aware that non-adherence is a significant public health problem, individual patients do not readily disclose their non-adherence without specific efforts to detect and quantify adherence.¹⁵ There is good evidence that health professionals can encourage readiness to quit smoking. Wilson et al demonstrate that even three-minutes of counselling can increase the rate of quitting by 5-10%.¹⁶ When different health professionals such

as pharmacists, doctors and nurses jointly counsel patients, the impact is greater. To illustrate, recent quitting was enhanced when 1,723 smokers received advice from different categories of health professionals (OR 2.37; 95% CI 1.15-4.88).¹⁷

A USA study reported that directions for dosing were provided to only 60% of patients who received counselling and only 33% patients were informed of the duration of use and adverse effects.¹⁸ Providing more information about medications (eg, how and when it should be taken, need for medication and adverse effects) improves adherence, partly because it improves the likelihood of understanding on how and why to take their medications.¹⁹

Over the years, attention towards ensuring compliance has been diminishing, because adherence to therapy is being considered to be exclusively the patient's responsibility. This is particularly troublesome in COPD patients because 50% of patients struggle to use a metered-dose inhaler properly. Each medication with its inhaler has different characteristics that vary between individuals in terms of: (1) internal resistance (2) intra-thoracic deposition (3) mechanism to check that the product was actually delivered and (4) time and duration of action. Understanding the above would definitely foster good adherence with the therapy because it would maximize inhaler-efficacy.²⁰ Poor inhaler technique and patients' beliefs about illness are associated with dismal outcomes.¹² Further, lack of perceived benefit has been associated with 30% of patients intentionally discontinuing their therapy.²¹

India has very little published data on clinical pharmacist-led patient self-management in COPD. Studies have shown that pharmacist-led, continuous, individualized patient education that identifies and recognizes psychosocial components of patient behavior can enhance overall satisfaction with health care experience by reducing emergency department visits, improving adherence and HRQoL. 5,6,²²

Acute shortage of physicians in India, chiefly owing to suboptimal educational opportunities and extensive migration of trained professionals to developed Western countries, poses a major problem that India shares with the developing world as a whole.²³ The overworked physicians appear to severely limit the implementation of quality healthcare delivery in India and many developing nations. Counselling the patient is either non-existent or ritualistic, and remains a low priority even in very prestigious hospitals. Therefore India needs to build an inclusive team of trained health professionals that includes clinical pharmacists. 'Task-sharing' with non-physician health professionals like clinical pharmacists, apart from being both feasible and less resource intensive, would go a long way in restricting the problems of COPD, its

associated vulnerabilities and consequent familial, social and economic impact.²³

In India, not many studies have been conducted to detect and analyse the economic, clinical and humanistic (adherence and HRQoL) outcomes in COPD patients. Moreover, healthcare in India is dominantly guided by physicians, with suboptimal support from non-physician health professionals. Therefore we took up this study to evaluate the effectiveness of clinical pharmacist intervention on COPD outcomes in a tertiary rohini super speciality hospital.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design:

The effectiveness of clinical pharmacist intervention on outcomes in COPD patients was assessed through an open-labelled randomized controlled study, over 1 year period.

Inclusion Criteria:

- ❖ COPD patients (Based on GOLD guidelines)
- ❖ Male and female (Age ≥ 40 to ≤ 70 years)
- ❖ Willingness to participate in the study by signing the informed consent form

Exclusion Criteria:

- ❖ Clinically unstable patients (as assessed by consultant physician)
- ❖ Moderate to severe learning difficulties
- ❖ Already attended pulmonary rehabilitation programme
- ❖ Severe Mobility problems

Study Subjects:

The study subjects were selected based on inclusion criteria (confirmed diagnosis of COPD as per GOLD guidelines) and willingness to participate by signing the informed consent (APPENDIX III and IV). Patients were randomly assigned to two groups (Intervention group [IG] and Control group [CG]) by the envelop method.¹⁵⁷

Baseline assessment:

After randomization, baseline data for each patient were collected by a custom designed and validated case record form. The collected data included demographics, disease characteristics, respiratory and non-respiratory medications and medication regimen. The patients were also asked to self-complete a set of three questionnaires (English or

Kannada version), namely (1) Bristol COPD knowledge questionnaire (BCKQ)¹⁵⁸ (Appendix V) (2) Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS)¹⁵ (Appendix VI) and (3) disease-specific HRQoL questionnaire; StGeorge Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ).¹⁵⁹ (Appendix VII)

Follow up assessment:

The assessments were repeated at 6, 12, 18 and 24 months in both the groups except for FEV₁ values. FEV₁ values were evaluated at only 12 months and 24 months (only minimal short term variations have been reported in COPD).

Study Material used:

Case record form (CRF) (Appendix VIII) – A case record form was designed and validated to collect the necessary information from the patient medical records and by a personal interview. CRF captures relevant data such as demographics, complaints on admission, history (social, medication and medical), laboratory reports, duration of hospitalization, drugs administered, details of ventilation and daily progress.

Study questionnaires:

- (1) BCKQ was employed to assess the effectiveness of patient education to cope with COPD. This consists of 13 questions with 5 items relating to pathophysiology of COPD, breathing and exercise, energy conservation and medications. [Scoring: correct responses = 1, incorrect responses = 0 and unsure responses receiving no score]. Higher the score, greater the knowledge level.
- (2) MMAS, which measures adherence through four Yes/No response items, accounts for the various reasons for non-adherence namely: forgetting, carelessness, stopping when feeling better and stopping when feeling worse. [Scoring: 'YES' = 0, 'NO' = 1]. MMAS scores range between 0 and 4.
- (3) SGRQ is a supervised, self-administered measure, designed specifically for patients with chronic airway disease. The SGRQ has been validated to measure the health impairment and responsiveness to therapy in patients with chronic airflow limitation. SGRQ scores are calculated for three components: (1) symptoms (2) activity and (3) impact. The total score for all items provides the overall picture of the patient's respiratory health. Scoring range for each component varies from 0 to 100, with the lowest scores indicating the highest level of health. A change in the mean score of 4 units has been validated as a clinically significant threshold.

Treatment Cost

Direct estimated medicine cost: - was calculated before and after the intervention, based on the data collected from CRF and personal interview.

Medication charges: - These included the cost of glucocorticoids, anticholinergics, antibiotics, methylxanthines and bronchodilators (Cost of medicines used to treat non respiratory conditions have been excluded). Medications refunds, etc were considered for accurately estimating the medicine costs.

Clinical Pharmacist Intervention:

Patient interview and counselling were carried out in an environment conducive for capturing patients' perceptions accurately. Patients recruited under IG were educated by the clinical pharmacists about symptom management, inhaler technique and their importance. Patient information leaflets (PILs) describing the above techniques were prepared and distributed to patients enrolled under IG, for reinforcing the content delivered through counselling. The counselling sessions and PILs (APPENDIX IX) laid emphasis on (1) importance of medication compliance, (2) need for smoking cessation, (3) simple exercise, (4) proper use of inhaler devices and (5) need for timely follow up by pulmonary medicine department. Each patient was followed up for a period of two years and HRQoL was periodically re-assessed after every six months. Patients were further persuaded by monthly telephone calls for ensuring medication adherence and timely follow ups. During follow up, patients in IG were further trained for proper use of inhaler devices and were motivated for medication adherence.

Control patients:

CG received standard hospital care, but did not receive the structured intervention by the clinical pharmacist.

Preparation of PILs:

PILs were developed based on model leaflets collected from different sources such as GOLD guidelines, Micromedex database, "Patient UK" etc. The contents of the leaflet were appropriately revised and validated by pulmonologists. Readability of the designed PIL was computed online (www.readability-score.com) by (1) Flesch Readability Ease (FRE) and (2) Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level (FK-GL). Layout and design characteristics of the PIL were assessed by Baker Able Leaflets Design (BALD) method.¹⁶⁰

Sample size:

In accordance with published literature, we estimated the minimum sample size of 103 in each group, in order to demonstrate a minimum clinical significance of 5% (power = 80%). Taking into account a 20% potential dropout rate, target sample size was estimated to be 260 patients (130 CG and 130 IG). Data analysis:

Statistical analyses (Data screening, descriptive statistics and univariate analysis) were performed using SPSS version 20.0. Categorical data were represented by mean \pm SD and nominal data by % frequency. Differences between CG and IG were

assessed for statistical significance by student t test for SGRQ and BCKQ. Chi square was used for MMAS. P-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 13: Baseline characteristics of study population

Characteristics	CG	IG	P-value
Age (Mean \pm SD) ^a	61.1 \pm 8.4	60.6 \pm 7.9	0.67
Gender (Male, %) ^b	94.4	96.9	0.08
Socioeconomic status ¹⁶¹ (%) ^b	0.73		
Lower	35.8	37.4	
Upper lower	30.5	29.8	
Middle	23.7	22.6	
Upper middle	7.1	6.4	
Upper	2.9	3.8	
FEV1 % (Mean \pm SD) ^a	41.9 \pm 14.7	44.4 \pm 14.5	0.16
Smoking Status (%) ^b	0.24		
Ex-Smoker	43.1	46.2	
Current smoker	56.9	53.8	
Pack years (Mean \pm SD) ^a	21.7 \pm 12.6	23.2 \pm 11.4	0.42
Duration of COPD (Mean \pm SD) ^a	15.3 \pm 5.7	14.6 \pm 6.6	0.36
Severity as per GOLD (%) ^b	0.34		
Mild	12.7	13.8	
Moderate	21.9	20.1	
Severe	45.4	47.6	
Very severe	20.0	18.5	
No. of Medications (Mean \pm SD) ^a	7.2 \pm 2.1	6.3 \pm 1.7	0.68
Co-morbid conditions (%) ^b	74	69	0.64

IG- Intervention group, CG- Control group, SD- standard deviation, FEV1-Forced expiratory volume in one second, COPD - Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, GOLD- Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease

^a Data were analysed by t test

^b Data were analysed by Chi square

Presence of co-morbidities

Out of 260 patients, 74% in CG and 69% in IG had co-morbidities. Co-morbidities (in decreasing order of percentage) in CG and IG, were (a) hypertension (24 vs 22), (b) diabetes mellitus (22 vs 20), (c) ischemic heart disease (18 vs 16), (d) others (10 vs 11). Others includeskin diseases, gastro esophageal disorders, arthritis and pulmonary artery hypertension. No co-morbidities were reported by 26 % in CG and 31 % in IG. Figure 3 depicts the above results.

Figure 3: Co-morbidities in COPD patients

Infections in COPD patients

Infections were present in 78.5% patients [77% (CG) vs 80% (IG)]. Majority had gram negative infections (22% in CG vs 23% IG) followed by gram positive (15% vs 18%). Figure 4 and 5 show the status of infections and type of bacteria detected respectively.

Figure 4: Status of infections in COPD patients

Figure 5: Types of bacteria in COPD patients

Clinical features of COPD patients

The most frequently reported symptom was dyspnoea [90.5% in CG vs 89% in IG], followed by cough with sputum [80% vs 82%], rhonchi [66.2% vs 65%], wheezing [51% vs 47%]. Table 14 depicts the various clinical presentations in COPD patients during study period.

Table 14: Clinical presentations in COPD patients

Clinical features	CG (%)	IG (%)
Dyspnoea	90.5	89.07
Cough with sputum	80.00	82.15
Rhonchi	66.20	65.00
Wheeze	51.02	47.30
Crepitations	33.45	30.25
Decreased breath sounds	30.28	28.23
Fever	28.17	29.31
Chest pain	16.20	18.00
Decreased chest movements	14.79	13.67
Dry cough	14.00	18.00
Barrel shaped chest	09.15	08.95
Generalized weakness	07.75	15.76

Prescription pattern of drugs in COPD patients

In the present study, 6 categories of drugs were prescribed to the patients in CG and IG. The categories of drugs include – glucocorticoids (54% vs 53%), anti-cholinergic (24% vs 25%), β_2 adrenergic agonist (23% vs 21%), phosphodiesterase inhibitors (22% vs 20%), antibiotics (19% vs 17%) and leukotriene receptor antagonist (9% vs 8%). Above results are depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Various drugs prescribed in COPD patients

Disease knowledge among COPD patients at different time intervals

At the baseline, BCKQ score were matched between CG and IG ($P>0.05$). In IG, BCKQ improved significantly at follow up, as a result of pharmacist intervention ($P<0.001$). The best improvement was noted at 24 months, giving a picture of wholesome progress. BCKQ score at different time intervals are shown in Table 15.

Table 15: Disease knowledge among COPD patients at different time intervals

BCKQ score (%) ^a	CG	IG	P-value
Baseline	46	48	0.67
6 months	48	64	0.001*
12 months	47	66	0.001*
18 months	48	68	0.001*
24 months	49	69	0.001*

BCKQ- Bristol COPD Knowledge Questionnaire,

CG-Control group, IG- Intervention group

^a Data were analysed by t test

*statistically significant

FEV1 values at different time points:

FEV1 was assessed at baseline, 12 months and 24 months for both patient groups. No significant improvement ($P>0.05$) in the mean FEV1 was observed throughout the study period between CG and IG after pharmacist intervention. Table 16 depicts the FEV1 values of COPD patients at different time intervals.

Table 16: FEV1 values of COPD patients at different time intervals.

FEV1 ^a (Mean±SD)	CG	IG	P-value
Baseline	41.9 ± 14.7	44.4 ± 14.5	0.16
12 months	38.4 ± 15.6	45.8 ± 13.8	0.10
24 months	37.9 ± 13.2	46.6 ± 15.9	0.86

FEV1: Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second, SD: Standard Deviation, CG: Control Group,

Medication adherence of COPD patients at different time interval: At the baseline, MMAS were matched between CG and IG ($P>0.05$). At follow up, MMAS improved significantly after pharmacist intervention in IG ($P<0.001$). The best improvement was observed at 24 months, giving a picture of wholesome improvement. MMAS at different time intervals are shown in Table 17

Table 17: Medication adherence of COPD patients at different time interval

% Adherence ^a	CG	IG	P-Value
<i>Baseline</i>			
Adherent	48	49	0.257
Non-adherent	52	51	
<i>6 months</i>			
Adherent	49	77	0.001*
Non-adherent	51	23	
<i>12 months</i>			
Adherent	49	78	0.001*
Non-adherent	51	22	
<i>18 months</i>			
Adherent	48	79	0.001*
Non-adherent	52	21	
<i>24 months</i>			
Adherent	49	80	0.001*
Non-adherent	51	20	

SD- standard deviation, CG-Control group, IG-Intervention group

^a Data were analysed by Chi-square, *statistically significant

Reasons for non-adherence among COPD patients: At baseline, we found that, carelessness about taking medicine was the major intentional reason for non-adherence (24% in CG vs 26% in IG). Among unintentional reasons, high cost of medicines (6% in CG vs 7% in IG) and running out of medicines (3% in CG vs 4% in IG) were the major reasons. At 24 months follow up, intentional reasons for non-adherence drastically decreased in IG, compared to CG. Table 18 depicts various reasons for non-adherence.

Table 18: Reasons for non-adherence among COPD patients

Reason for non-adherence	Baseline		24 Months	
	CG %	IG %	CG %	IG %
Intentional				
Carelessness about taking medicines	24	26	25	10
Stop taking medicines when feel better	17	16	15	07
Stopping when feeling worse	12	13	13	07
Forget to take medicines	10	09	11	08
Not beneficial	09	07	09	02
Fear of side effects	07	05	06	02
Fear of becoming dependent on treatment	06	06	07	03
Unintentional				
High cost of medicines	06	07	06	32
Running out of medicines	03	04	04	08
Complex dosing regimens	04	03	02	12
Old Age	02	04	02	09
Total	100	100	100	100

CG- Control group, IG-Intervention group

HRQoL at different time intervals in COPD patients: At the baseline, total SGRQ scores and its domains (symptoms, activity and impact) were matched between CG and IG ($P>0.05$). In IG, total SGRQ score and its subscales improved significantly at follow-up after pharmacist intervention ($P<0.001$). Further, differences in the total SGRQ score and its domains, between CG and IG, surpassed the critical 4 point threshold, indicating positive outcomes. The best improvement was noted in the impact domain (8.16) at 24 months, giving a picture of wholesome improvement. SGRQ scores at different time intervals are shown in Table 19.

Total SGRQ score in IG & CG at different time intervals: At follow-up, IG reported statistically significant differences ($P<0.001$) in the total SGRQ score compared to CG (Figure 7). HRQoL uniformly improved in all three subscales namely

(1) symptoms, (2) activity and (3) impact (Table 19). While the total SGRQ scores of CG remained more or less unchanged, there was substantial improvement in IG (Figure 7). Even the 'activity' domain, which showed least improvement in response to pharmacist intervention, demonstrated a clinically significant ($P<0.001$) drop in SGRQ score (Table 17).

Figure 7: Total SGRQ score in CG & IG at different time intervals

Table 19: HRQoL at different time intervals in COPD patients

SGRQ ^a	CG	IG	Unit differences (95% CI)	P-value
Baseline				
Symptoms	73.21	72.14	-1.07 (-2.32-1.92)	0.702
Activity	78.12	77.84	-0.28 (-0.89-0.74)	0.734
Impact	61.89	61.24	-0.35 (-0.67-0.84)	0.868
Total	68.40	68.50	-0.02 (-0.31-0.34)	0.913
6 Months				
Symptoms	73.81	66.83	-6.98 (-8.46- -5.32)	0.001*
Activity	76.23	71.20	-5.03 (-7.53- -3.40)	0.001*
Impact	62.31	55.43	-6.88 (-8.21- -5.11)	0.001*
Total	68.30	61.70	-6.67 (-7.36- -5.97)	0.001*
12 Months				
Symptoms	74.01	66.36	-6.65 (-7.47- -4.89)	0.001*
Activity	77.56	72.51	-5.05 (-8.76- -4.46)	0.001*
Impact	63.21	56.32	-6.89 (-7.87- -4.72)	0.001*
Total	67.80	61.62	-7.09 (-7.77- -6.40)	0.001*
18 Months				
Symptoms	73.92	67.52	-6.40 (-8.10- -5.41)	0.001*
Activity	78.31	73.89	-4.42 (-6.84- -4.11)	0.001*
Impact	60.43	53.41	-7.02 (-7.67- -5.36)	0.001*
Total	68.50	61.31	-7.18 (-7.91- -6.44)	0.001*
24 Months				
Symptoms	71.96	65.74	-6.22 (-7.36- -5.81)	0.001*
Activity	77.89	73.63	-4.23 (-6.13- -4.02)	0.001*
Impact	62.03	53.87	-8.16 (-9.13- -7.14)	0.001*
Total	68.50	60.40	-8.14 (-8.85- -7.43)	0.001*

IG- Intervention group, CG-Control group, CI- confident interval,
* Statistically significant at $P < 0.05$, ^aData were analysed by t test

Direct medicine cost based on severity in COPD patients:

At baseline, medicine cost was highly correlated with disease severity, with mild COPD incurring the least cost per patient per 6 months (CG=1978 INR vs IG=1819 INR). Predictably, very severe COPD incurred the highest cost (CG=4130 INR vs IG=4213 INR). Direct medicine cost decreased significantly after pharmacist intervention in IG at all levels of severity [mild COPD (CG=2760 INR vs IG=2118 per patient) and very severe COPD (CG=4318 INR vs IG=3121 INR per patient)]. Cost saved by structured pharmacist-led intervention was found to be 642 INR in mild patients and 1197 INR in very severe patients. Table 20 shows the direct medicine cost based on severity.

Table 20: Direct medicine cost based on severity in COPD patients

Severity of COPD	Baseline (cost in INR)		24 months (cost in INR)		Cost saved by structured pharmacist-led intervention	
	CG	IG	CG	IG	CG ^a (24 months)	IG ^b (baseline)
Stage-I (Mild)	1978	1819	2760	2118	642	-299
Stage-II (Moderate)	2351	2574	2818	2314	504	260
Stage-III (Severe)	3562	3467	3871	2874	997	593
Stage-IV (Very severe)	4130	4213	4318	3121	1197	1092

CG: Control Group, IG: Intervention Group, COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, INR: Indian rupee

^a Compared to CG (24 months), ^b Compared to IG (Baseline)

Estimated direct medicine cost to COPD patients at baseline

Median estimated direct medicine cost at baseline was matched between CG and IG (2456 vs 2475). The medicine cost ranged from a minimum of 1987 in CG and 1719 in IG to a maximum of 4138 (CG) and 4218 (IG). Figure 8 shows the boxplot of cost comparison between CG and IG at baseline.

DISCUSSION

Pharmacists can prevent DRPs and achieve optimal outcomes from drug therapy, especially in chronic diseases.¹⁶² To the best of our knowledge, this is the first randomized controlled study from India that describes the highly significant impact of patient-education by clinical pharmacists on COPD outcomes. Even the few Indian studies that previously assessed HRQoL are either cross sectional or observational without considering pharmacist intervention.^{127,128,130,132,134} Key findings of our study highlight the importance of patient- education by pharmacists in COPD patients.

Elderly males constitute the majority of COPD patients both in India and Northern Ireland.^{5, 127,130} However, Northern Ireland and Indian patients differ in their smoking habits. While Northern Ireland patients were mostly ex-smokers, COPD patients recruited in our study were mostly current smokers.⁵ This difference is primarily on account of deficiencies in the health care system to educate, motivate and counsel patients on the importance of smoking cessation.

COPD greatly limits patients' daily activities, thereby compromising their QoL.¹⁶³ Patients in the present study demonstrated a low HRQoL at baseline, because most of them belonged to severe (GOLD III) category. However, HRQoL of IG reported more than four-unit change in SGRQ ($P < 0.001$) at 6 months post intervention, when compared with CG. This improvement, in all three subscales (symptom, impact and activity) is sustained over time at 12, 18 and 24-months post intervention (Table 19). This suggests

that pharmacist-led intervention is useful in ensuring patient health at various time points during follow-up. Despite having no previous history of educational interventions for COPD in India, we were able to demonstrate the value of pharmacist-led intervention in improving outcomes. Improvement in SGRQ scores is greater in our study than that of Northern Ireland study,⁵ demonstrating the significant impact of even modest interventions in India.

Patients recruited in our study had poorer health at baseline compared to a similar New Zealand study (SGRQ Score=68.4 vs 37.2).¹⁶⁴ Although the New Zealand study contradicts the value of pharmacist-led intervention, upon closer examination, one can see that the subjects in the New Zealand study were much healthier than their Indian counterparts. The very big gap between the baseline SGRQ scores of patients in New Zealand and India (68.4 vs 37.2) demonstrates tremendous opportunity for pharmacist-led intervention in India.

A systematic review and meta-analysis by Rea et al indicated that only 1 of 7 studies reported a significant improvement in lung function in patients with COPD.^{6,153} Consistent with this findings, effects of the intervention on FEV1 in our study were not statistically significant ($P>0.05$). This is because COPD is a progressive disease characterized by irreversible damage; FEV1 is difficult to change and therefore is not expected to be sensitive to pharmacist-led intervention programmes.^{5,6,165}

Our study showed that pharmacist-led intervention significantly improved ($P<0.001$) the knowledge (BCKQ) about the disease, symptoms, and medications. This is in agreement with a study by Thomas et al which demonstrates that clinical pharmacist-led patient education (three occasions over a period of 3 months) improved the knowledge, attitude and practice in COPD patients of South India.¹⁶⁶ A RCT by Hill et al also shows that education sessions (two one-on-one 60 min) with COPD patients is feasible in primary care and is associated with significant improvements in patient knowledge (BCKQ) in intervention group.¹⁶⁷ This study highlights the opportunities for brief disease-specific education delivered in primary care to optimize disease-specific knowledge. Similar findings were evident from a 6 months self-management programme for COPD patients in UK, which demonstrated significant improvement in BCKQ score ($P<0.05$).¹⁶⁸ Therefore, pharmacist-led COPD disease-specific education can improve the knowledge of the patient, thereby enhancing both medication adherence and HRQoL.

A systematic review on COPD management suggests that educational interventions should cover topics recommended by the COPD guidelines, in addition to task-sharing, facilitated by a multidisciplinary team of health professionals.¹⁶⁹ COPD is more common in poorer and uneducated Indian patients (Table 1). Poverty is inextricably linked to illiteracy, high smoking rates, crowding, poor sanitation, malnutrition and lack of access to health care.¹⁷⁰ The extreme shortage of physicians in India further magnifies the role of pharmacists in patient education.

Educational intervention is an economical and feasible strategy, especially in the context of the ever-increasing burden of non-communicable diseases in resource-poor developing nations like India. Our results (Table 17) revealed that, medication adherence can be improved significantly ($P<0.001$) in COPD patients by structured pharmacist-led intervention. Gallefos et al demonstrate that, an individualized treatment plan with a self-management training programme, by a nurse or physiotherapist, can improve patient outcomes in COPD within one year.¹⁴⁰ Previous studies by Mahour et al and Jarab et al demonstrated that pharmacist-led

intervention improved medication adherence in COPD patients in Northern Ireland and Jordan respectively.^{5,6}

Patients often have little or no understanding about their symptoms, exacerbations and specific actions to be taken in such situations of emergency.¹⁷¹ When patients are given an opportunity to identify / discuss their concerns about medications and/or life style, fears can be allayed and barriers can be identified. Medication adherence in COPD is generally poor (about 50%).¹⁷² Most frequent reasons for non-adherence in our study, at baseline, were carelessness, stopping when they 'feel better', stopping when 'feel worse' and forgetting. This is consistent with previous studies.

The goal of improving adherence in COPD patients should emphasise on maintaining clinically meaningful improvements in health status and reducing healthcare costs, rather than simply mandating compliance to physician recommendations.¹⁹ Health professionals and caregivers contribute to patients' perception of their disease, healthcare and medication and eventually, adherence. Previous reports have endorsed the strategies employed by us in improving medication adherence, namely (1) continuous monitoring of care (2) explaining the rationale for prescription (3) providing information about disease and drug regimens in both verbal and written formats (4) assessment of medication adherence (5) follow-up

supervision and (6) participation in self-management programmes.

Wilson et al demonstrated that one-third of patients did not talk to their doctor about their medicines during the previous year.¹⁷⁶ Studies conducted even in developed countries such as USA, suggest that 35% of patients receive no instruction on how to take new medications, while up to 60% receive only dosing directions.^{177,178} Overworked physicians and paucity of trained doctors in resource-poor settings obligate task-sharing to non-physician healthcare providers like clinical pharmacists, who can simplify treatment regimens and enhance compliance. Task sharing is both feasible and less resource-intensive and would go a long way in the management of COPD.

Our study corroborates previous reports that demonstrate the supreme importance of clinical pharmacist-driven patient education, which reinforces medication adherence and inhaler technique at every follow up.^{5,6, 179-181} This is in agreement with a USA study in which pharmacists in the patient-care team could reduce adverse drug events by 66%, with 99% acceptance from physicians.

Our study demonstrates a strong correlation between disease severity and direct medicine cost in COPD. Hilleman et al reported the same results in USA,¹⁸³ demonstrating that, disease severity increased cost. Previous Indian observational studies also revealed that treatment cost is highly correlated to disease severity.^{184,185} Bourbeau et al and Gallefoss have demonstrated that self-management plan leads to economic benefits in COPD patients.^{19,140} This is in agreement with our study (Table 20).

Even the medicine cost saved by structured pharmacist-led intervention in IG varied from mild to severe COPD. Our results conclusively demonstrate the significant role of pharmacist in diminishing healthcare cost in India. It has been observed that in many situations medical insurance companies persuade physicians to prescribe injectable medications, without rationale. Though medically unjustifiable, such practices are supposed to facilitate the payment of a rightful insurance claim. Such illogical practices may also be attributed to a suboptimal role of the clinical pharmacists working for the insurance sector. Prescription audits are supposed to ensure that patients covered by insurance receive appropriate prescriptions. To illustrate, insurance companies operating in other countries (Eg. Saudi Arabia) employ qualified trained pharmacists as 'prescription auditors'. India is yet to demonstrate the value of such roles for the pharmacists in the medical insurance sector, leading to enormous economic

burden, in addition to the multiple intangible costs associated with illness.

Healthcare cost can be minimized especially in chronic disorders by implementing structured pharmacist-led intervention, which reduce DRPs such as drug use without indication, wrong route of administration, improper drug selection, etc. Previous studies have revealed that patient education can significantly reduce the healthcare cost including the intangible costs associated with illness such as loss of work days, absenteeism, expenses incurred by the care giver, transport, food and shelter, etc.

Pharmacists should be ideally placed in the healthcare system because they act as a link between patients and physicians. Even in the context of extreme shortage of physicians, the role of pharmacist in India remains that of a retailer engaged in the sale of medicines. We believe that, our study strongly endorses expanding the pharmacists' role, an economically viable strategy for resource-poor nations like India.

CONCLUSION:

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first randomized controlled study from India that unequivocally confirms the effectiveness of pharmacist-led intervention on COPD outcomes. We observed a significant difference in all the subscales of SGRQ in IG, at all follow up time points. MMAS was also improved in IG after structured intervention. Patient knowledge improved in IG, while FEV1 was not significantly improved. Treatment cost was drastically decreased in IG after pharmacist-led intervention.

Patient education strategy is particularly appropriate for poorer countries like India, where health education and patient counselling are either completely ignored or minimally implemented. Enhancing patient self-efficacy as part of self-management education is also important to promote long term adherence. Shared decision making during the initial and regular follow-up visits helps to augment the partnership between patient and physician, thereby facilitating adherence, improving patient outcomes and thereby diminishing the economic and societal burden associated with COPD.

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